
Environment and its influence

Photoperiod sensitivity of Rayada rices

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Rayada, unlike traditional deepwater rice varieties, has cold tolerance at seedling stage, lacks seed dormancy, has a very long growth duration (11 mo), and is cultivated in 3.7-6 m water depth.

The Rayada rices in Bangladesh are sown with boro rices as a mixed crop. Boro varieties are photoperiod insensitive and are usually harvested in Apr or May when Rayada plants are vegetative. Rayada rices continue to grow under subsequent deepwater conditions and do not flower until late Sep and Oct when day length is less than 12 hours, Rayada rices do not respond to short photoperiod in Feb and early Mar when planted in Nov, and always flower in Sep and Oct. Is this group of cultivars a photoperiod-sensitive type with a long basic vegetative phase (BVP)? We tried to verify this assumption.

Five strains of Rayada conserved by the IRRI International Rice Germplasm Center were used. Habiganj (HBJ) aman 1, a deepwater rice variety, was the photoperiod-sensitive check and HBJ boro 5 was the insensitive check. Plants received 10, 12, 14, and 16 h photoperiods starting at seeding dates. Plants that did not flower after 140 days of growth were dissected and checked for panicle primordia.

HBJ aman 1 and Rayada strains flowered at 10 and 12 h photoperiod and re-

Days to flower, basic vegetative phase (BVP) and photoperiod sensitive phase (PSP) of five strains of Rayada, HBJ aman 1, and HBJ boro 5 at different photoperiods.

Variety, strains	Days to flowering ^a at photoperiod of				BVP	PSP
	10 h	12 h	14 h	16 h		
Rayada 16-02	108	126	–	–	73	140+
Rayada 16-03	108	124	–	–	73	140+
Rayada 16-05	109	126	–	–	74	140+
Rayada 16-06	108	124	–	–	13	140+
Rayada 16-08	105	125	–	–	70	140+
HBJ aman 1	38	80	–	–	3	140+
HBJ boro 5	92	92	97	92	57	5

^aA dash (–) means the variety did not initiate panicles after 140 days of growth.

mained vegetative at 14 and 16 h photoperiods (see table). HBJ boro 5 flowered at all the photoperiod treatments, with similar flowering duration. Based on flowering behavior, both HBJ aman 1 and Rayada strains are strongly photoperiod sensitive with a long photoperiod-sensitive phase (PSP) and critical photoperiod of around 12 hours.

The BVP, which is synonymous with insensitive phase or juvenile stage of a variety, can be estimated by subtracting 35 days from the number of days from sowing to flowering when the plants are grown under optimum photoperiod. Although the BVP range reported in the literature varies from 10 to 63 days, none of the strongly photoperiod-sensitive varieties so far tested had a BVP of more than 49 days. Rayada strains had a 70- to 74-day BW.

On the basis of BVP and PSP duration, rice varieties are classified into four types.

Type A has a short BVP and PSP, type B has a long BVP and short PSP, and type C has short BVP and long PSP. Type D varieties with long BVP and PSP have not yet been reported, but present observations indicate Rayadas are type D.

Type D varieties were probably eliminated during domestication because they have an unusually long growth duration. That Rayada rices represent less than 10% of the total deepwater rices in Bangladesh substantiates this statement.

Although the different Rayada strains are strongly photoperiod-sensitive with a BVP of around 70 days and a critical photoperiod of around 12 h, they do not respond to shorter Feb and Mar photoperiods when planted in Nov. Low temperatures in Nov, Dec, and Jan may extend the already long BVP so that when the plant is ready for photoinduction, the day length is already longer than the critical photoperiod.

Rice-based cropping systems

Agroeconomic performance of six rice - wheat cropping patterns, Thakurgaon, Bangladesh

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In Bangladesh, 92% of the farmers grow rice on 74% of the cultivable land. Rice is about 93% and wheat is 5% of cereal grains production.

During the 1970s introduction of high yielding rice varieties from BRRI and modern wheat varieties from the Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute dramatically changed agriculture in Bangladesh. High yielding, short-duration,

photoperiod-insensitive rice varieties sometimes perform well in rice - wheat cropping patterns in some wheat-growing areas. Time of transplanted (t.) aman rice harvest, and planting time and growth duration of wheat varieties are critical to this cropping pattern. A late t. aman harvest delays wheat planting, which causes low yield because grain must ripen during hot, dry weather. To attain maximum